

Women Empowerment through Entrepreneurial Efficiency: A Study with reference to Rural SHGs

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ABSTRACT

Empowerment is a sparkling multifaceted procedure to allow women to recognize their uniqueness, place and supremacy in all spheres of life. Entrepreneurial efficiency is the ability to manage an enterprise. Quality of life is the perception that an individual has about their positioning in life. The present paper empirically aimed at relating these three important concepts of Women empowerment, Entrepreneurial Efficiency & quality of life in the context of Self Help Group women. The data was collected from 192 SHG entrepreneurs in Kadapa district. Statistical tools like KMO bartlet test, Factor analysis and multiple regression were applied using SPSS package. The study revealed that there is a positive and significant impact of entrepreneurial efficiency on women empowerment and empowerment influences the quality of life of SHG entrepreneurs.

1. Introduction

Empowerment of women and gender equality recognized globally as a key element to achieve progress in all areas. Empowerment with respect to women's development is a way of essential, exigent and overcoming of barriers in a woman's life through which she increases her ability to shape her life and environment (Murthy 2012). It is an active process which should enable women to realize their full identity and power in all spheres of life (Vijayalakshmi, Narayana Gowda, Jamuna, Babu, Ray and Sajjan, 2012).

Women comprise more or less half of the total population in the world. But, in almost all the societies, women have less power than men, have less control over resources and receive lesser wages for their work. They remain as an 'invisible' work force. Inevitably, all this affects women's capacity to open up, grow, develop, exceed and excel (Bayeh, 2016). It is inopportune that because of centuries of disinterest, ignorance and conservatism, the actual and potential role of women in the society has been ignored, preventing them from making their rightful contribution to social progress. With regard to their multidimensional responsibilities, it is required to empower women socially, economically and technologically to enable them to stand in society on their own with confidence (Sharma & Varma, 2008).

Economic independence is the need of the hour. Participation in income generating activities and entrepreneurial activities helps in the overall empowerment of women. Empowering women through education, ideas, consciousness, mobilization and most importantly entrepreneurial approach can enable self-reliant and self-confidant which lead to quality of life (Maggu 2016).

Quality of life (QoL) is a model level that comprises of the expectations of an individual for a good life. These expectations are directed by the principles, goals and socio-cultural context in which an individual lives. It is a

multidimensional concept that defines a standard level for emotional, physical, material and social well-being.

Women membership in Self Help Groups have shaped incredible impact upon the life pattern and style of poor women and have empowered them at various levels not only as individuals but also as members of the family members of the community and the society as whole (Kondal, 2014). In various national policies and developmental programmes, emphasis has been given on organizing women in Self Help Groups and thus, marks the beginning of a major process of empowering women. It is also felt to equip the women with necessary skills in the modern trades, which could make them economically self-reliant (Lina & Krishna, 2014). Women must be empowered by enhancing their awareness, knowledge; skills and technology use efficiency, thereby, facilitating quality of life and overall development of the society. The concept of Self Help Groups (SHGs) is proving to be a helpful instrument for the empowerment and quality of life of women (Sharma & Varma, 2008 et al.).

2. Literature Review

A Self Help Group (SHG) is a group of concerning 10 to 20 individuals, usually women, from a related class and region, who come jointly to form savings and credit organization. They pooled financial resources to make small interest bearing loans to their members (Mochi & Vahoniya, 2015). Today, rural women have been suffering a lot due to the feeling of helplessness and lack of Decision-making capabilities in financial matters. Self help groups (SHGs) are the current advance for them which could enable them to come forward and make them self dependent and self employed. (Kanakalatha, 2017). Self-help groups (SHGs) have played a significant role to provide women their rightful place in the society and have propelled their inclusion in to the larger economic and political systems in India (Goswami, Dsilva & Chaudhary, 2018). Rural women belonging to all categories of caste with primary education or even illiterate under the banner

of self-help groups (SHGs) had been earning not only income but feeling empowered (Chatterjee, 2016), the women associated with SHGs have economically benefited and the SHGs have greater impact on both economic and social aspects of the beneficiaries (Kanakalatha, et al).

Women are treated as an important human resource of the country and every state should try to make use of them as mediators of economic growth and development. Support for women entrepreneurship is one of the ways for that. Foremost part of national economic development is contributed by rural economy. Rural women have to be initiated to step out of home and take responsibilities in the society (Meenakshi, Subrahmanyam & Ravichandran, 2013). Developing entrepreneurial skills among women will be a good approach for women empowerment and this would elevate social status of women (Gopika, John & Jose, 2015). The specialists in economic development have considered entrepreneurship development as a possible approach to empower women (Neha Pandey 2014). Women empowerment is a consequence

of women entrepreneurship. Women entrepreneurship positively and significantly leads to women empowerment in emerging economies like India (Stanzin Mantok, 2016).

Women's empowerment and work performance are two of the most important issues of concern (Kimpah & Raudeliuniene, 2014) Empowering women to participate in economic life is one way to improve the quality of life for women, families and communities (Subramaniama, Tanb, Maniamc & Alid, 2013). Through the women's empowerment, women challenge the existing norms and culture in efforts to promote their well being (Hemavathy Nithyanandhana & Norma Mansorb, 2015). The empowerment tools do influence the employee's performance. Meanwhile, Performance Appraisal mediates the relationship between empowerment and employee performance (Rajalingam, Junaimah Abdul Ghani, Bashawir, 2015). The workplace designed with flexibility has a positive impact on women's empowerment and quality of life (Subramaniama, Tanb, Maniamc & Alid, et al 2013).

3. Conceptual Framework

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis

4. Objectives of the Study

After reviewing the different research works pertaining to empowerment and quality of life of women is depended on various factors and entrepreneurial efficiency is also seemed to be one of the influencing factors; hence this paper is aimed to

1. Investigate the impact of entrepreneurial efficiency factors on empowerment of SHG members
2. Study the influence of women empowerment on quality of life of SHG members

5. Hypothesis

H1: There is significant relationship between women entrepreneurial Efficiency factors and women empowerment

H2: There is significant relationship between women Empowerment factors and women Quality of life of SHG members

6. Methodology

This study is evidenced from rural women entrepreneurs of SHGs in YSR district of Andhra Pradesh. A multistage

random sampling has been adopted for the study. In the first stage, YSR District is divided into three geographical regions namely Kadapa, Rajampeta and Jammalamadugu revenue divisions. Two mandals from each region, chennur and vallur from Kadapa region, Sidhout and rajampet from Rajampeta region and mydukur and prodduturu from Jammalamadugu region were selected randomly in the second stage; and 18 Self Help Groups, three from each Mandal were chosen in the third stage. Finally 216 members, 12 members from each Self Help Group were picked up to collect the data. Out of 216 members 24 members were not found when the researcher tried to meet. So, the data were collected from 192 members. The data were collected during the month of January, 2019. Data collection was done with the help of pre-tested structured interview schedule. The interview schedule contains 30 questions framed on 5- point likert scale to find out the respondents strength of agreement. The secondary data was obtained from various published and unpublished records, journals, DRDA reports etc.

7. Analysis and Interpretation

Reliability Analysis

The reliability test was conducted to check the consistency, accuracy and stability of the tool used in the research. Cronbach alpha value is shown as 0.782 means all the items in schedule are at satisfactory level.

Table-1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.782	.752	30

KMO & Bartlet Test

Table-2: KMO and Bartlet Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.719
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3496.179
	df	435
	Sig.	.000

This test is carried to find out the suitability of the dataset to perform factor analysis. The Measures of Sampling Adequacy value is found as 0.719, which is greater than 0.6 revealed that sampling is adequate for factor analysis. The Sphericity value of Bartlett's Test is 0.000, which is < 0.05. Therefore, Factor analysis is chosen as a suitable technique for further investigation of the data.

Identifying the Significant Factor Loadings

We constructed factor loadings matrix called component matrix. It is common acceptance that, 0.5 and above is considered to be significant. All factor loadings of 0.5 and above have been considered for the study.

Table-3: Total Variance Explained by Different Variables

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	7.585	25.284	25.284	7.585	25.284	25.284	4.844	16.147	16.147
2	2.391	7.969	33.254	2.391	7.969	33.254	3.914	13.046	29.194
3	2.004	6.681	39.934	2.004	6.681	39.934	2.226	7.421	36.615
4	1.867	6.223	46.157	1.867	6.223	46.157	1.818	6.061	42.676
5	1.567	5.224	51.381	1.567	5.224	51.381	1.731	5.770	48.446
6	1.471	4.902	56.283	1.471	4.902	56.283	1.730	5.766	54.212
7	1.276	4.252	60.535	1.276	4.252	60.535	1.638	5.461	59.673
8	1.120	3.733	64.268	1.120	3.733	64.268	1.379	4.595	64.268
9	1.069	3.563	67.831						
10	.966	3.221	71.052						
11	.904	3.014	74.066						
12	.900	3.001	77.067						
13	.800	2.666	79.733						
14	.714	2.381	82.114						
15	.654	2.179	84.293						
16	.626	2.087	86.380						
17	.549	1.829	88.209						
18	.489	1.630	89.839						
19	.452	1.508	91.347						
20	.410	1.367	92.714						
21	.386	1.286	94.000						
22	.348	1.159	95.159						
23	.310	1.035	96.193						
24	.295	.983	97.176						
25	.260	.867	98.043						
26	.223	.742	98.785						
27	.186	.620	99.406						
28	.149	.497	99.903						
29	.018	.062	99.964						
30	.011	.036	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

As per the significance of factor loadings, eight factors have been extracted from 30 statements of the schedule.

Table-4: Principal component Analysis with Varimax Rotation:

Rotated Component Matrix ^a								
	Component							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
15.	.825	.289	-.164	.044	.164	-.125	.111	.036
27.	.805	.328	-.186	.038	.146	-.127	.112	.012
29.	.747	.003	.013	-.153	-.177	.151	-.067	-.221
14.	.741	.241	.043	.380	.005	-.038	-.174	-.040
26.	.739	.235	.039	.374	.039	-.066	-.137	-.028
30.	.726	.349	-.139	-.138	-.106	.024	.001	-.157
28.	.520	.406	-.075	.159	.358	-.119	-.042	.051
36.	.170	.779	.047	.135	-.108	.135	.008	.055
38.	.143	.772	-.078	-.125	.132	-.108	.044	.020
37.	.199	.754	-.024	.015	.012	-.198	.058	-.107
32.	.365	.579	.133	.130	-.139	.190	-.180	-.069
40.	.376	.559	-.239	.017	.193	.076	-.063	-.020
34.	.104	.525	-.058	.451	.185	-.016	.025	-.009
19.	.053	-.037	.694	.048	-.139	.030	.041	-.020
12.	-.374	-.134	.669	.070	.168	-.154	-.028	-.180
11.	-.198	.150	.586	.140	-.097	-.021	.107	.468
35.	.355	.004	.514	.339	-.100	-.072	-.050	-.186
31.	.425	-.019	.513	.250	-.098	.129	.135	-.083
9.	.079	.074	.077	.652	-.015	.051	.012	.097
13.	-.189	-.127	-.411	.514	.224	-.157	.057	.019
16.	.097	.119	-.031	.256	.747	-.038	.301	.017
20.	.051	.035	.036	.204	.627	-.105	.150	.048
21.	.023	-.077	-.070	-.122	.045	.760	-.012	.075
25.	-.007	.045	.101	.355	.085	.632	.102	-.227
22.	-.224	.085	-.315	.151	-.222	.512	-.217	.120
18..	.000	.068	.185	-.026	.033	-.013	.817	-.111
23.	-.269	-.125	-.385	.351	-.292	-.107	.508	-.082
17.	-.044	-.064	.030	-.062	.373	.474	.507	.159
24.	-.120	-.148	-.113	.075	.063	.021	-.228	.741
10.	-.088	-.041	.502	-.072	-.155	.042	.270	.555
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.								
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.								
a. Rotation converged in 23 iterations.								

After the matrix was obtained, in which the variables have significant factor loadings, then names are assigned to the pattern of loadings. All the 30 statements have been considered for collecting data as the factor loadings for all questions are more than 0.5. The value of positive influence on Social Relationship (Q18), Income level (Q19), Bank credit worthiness (Q20), strong vision and mission and knowledge on the dynamics of running an enterprise (Q21), welfare measures through the enterprise (Q22), Sound technology adoption and implementation (Q23) and trained to understand and utilise the modern technologies (Q24) are set as factor 1 and named **Empowerment**. The values of Economic status

(Q25), Nutrition and Health (Q26), Housing (Q27), Material Possession (Q28), Act against Social Evils (Q29) and Personal Grooming (Q30) are for factor 2, named as **Personal Quality of life**.

For factor 3, the values of Planning of activities (Q1), Knowing and assigning of duties and responsibilities(Q2), Motivation and Supervision(Q3), Co-ordination with others (Q4) and Corrective action /Problem solving attitude (Q5) are set named as **Managerial Efficiency**. For factor 4, Technical Efficiency, Production and manufacturing activities (Q6) and Adoption of the latest technology (Q7) are considered.

Enterprise Development and Continuous Improvement (Q14) and Effective change management (Q15) are named as **Operational Efficiency** factor. Knowledge on market conditions (Q7), Buying, selling, and exchange activities (Q8) and Preparation of programmes for attracting customers (Q9), named as **Commercial Efficiency**; For the factor 7, Budget estimation and preparation (Q11), Fund rising capacity and Allocation (Q12) and Systematic analysis and disciplined execution (Q13) are set, they named as **Financial Efficiency** factors. And finally factor 8 is named as **Public relations** and questions such as Relation with customers and dealers and suppliers (Q16) Building loyalty (Q17) are considered.

8. Impact of Entrepreneurial Efficiency factors on empowerment

To measure the impact of entrepreneurial efficiency factors on empowerment of self help group members, multiple regression analysis was carried. Multiple regression analysis was run to study the effect of independent variables such as Managerial, technical, commercial, financial, Operational and Public relations, dependent variable empowerment. The relationships were tested at the significance level of $p < 0.05$. P value which fall between 0.01 and 0.05 shows that there is a relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. Independent variables with higher beta values contribute greater influence to the dependent variables.

Table-5(a): Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.755 ^a	.726	.699	.167
a. Predictors: (Constant), RELATION, Technical, Managerial Efficiency, FINANCIAL, COMMERCIAL, OPERATIONAL				

Table-5(b): ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	37.834	6	6.306	4.629	.000 ^b
	Residual	262.886	193	1.362		
	Total	300.720	199			
a. Dependent Variable: 33. Overall Empowerment						
b. Predictors: (Constant), RELATION, Technical, Managerial Efficiency, FINANCIAL, COMMERCIAL, OPERATIONAL						

Table- 5 (c): Multiple Regression Co-efficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.557	.846		5.386	.000
Managerial	.139	.068	.147	2.041	.043
Financial	.289	.118	.174	2.446	.015
Commercial	-.362	.117	.221	3.102	.002
Technical	.025	.147	.012	.168	.867
Operational	.444	.164	.201	2.712	.007
Relations	-.123	.056	-.155	-2.191	.030
a. Dependent Variable: 33. Overall Empowerment					

It is observed from the Table 5 (a), that R square value is 0.726 explains the strong linear relationship between independent variable Entrepreneurial efficiency factors and dependent variable overall empowerment of SHG members. For all the entrepreneurial factors such as Managerial (0.43),

financial (0.15), commercial (0.002), Operational (0.007) and Public relations (0.30) except Technical efficiency, p values are less than 0.05. Hence, all these factors have the significant impact on empowerment. Technical efficiency is not influencing the empowerment as its p value recorded as $> .05$.

9. Impact of empowerment on Quality of life

Table-6(a): Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.846 ^a	.766	.712	.961
a. Predictors: (Constant), 32. Training, 29. strong vision and mission and knowledge , 28. Bank credit worthiness, 31. Sound technology adoption and implementation , 26. Social Relationship , 27. Income level , 30. welfare measures through the enterprise				

Table-6(b)ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	126.804	7	18.115	19.604	.000 ^b
	Residual	177.416	192	.924		
	Total	304.220	199			
a. Dependent Variable: 41. Overall Quality						
b. Predictors: (Constant), 32. Training, 29. strong vision and mission and knowledge , 28. Bank credit worthiness, 31. Sound technology adoption and implementation , 26. Social Relationship , 27. Income level , 30. welfare						

measures through the enterprise

Table-6(c): Multiple Regression Co-efficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.570	.279		2.043	.042
	Social Relationship	-.146	.076	-.158	-1.924	.050
	Income level status	.354	.080	.400	4.412	.000
	Bank credit worthiness	.257	.074	.252	3.454	.001
	Vision, Mission & knowledge	.090	.073	.098	1.239	.217
	welfare measures	-.202	.084	-.236	-2.409	.017
	Technology adoption & implementation	.304	.067	.324	4.524	.000
	Training & Skills	.106	.063	.116	1.676	.095
a. Dependent Variable: 41.Overall Quality						

Table 6 (a) in which R square value is 0.766 shows a strong linear relationship between independent variable empowerment and dependent variable overall quality of life SHG members. Table 6 (c) depicts that the empowerment components' p values for social relationship (0.05), income level status (0.000), bank credit worthiness (0.001), welfare measures (0.017) technology adoption and implementation (0.000) and Training and skills (0.095), are less than 0.05. Hence, all these components are statistically significant. There is significant impact on quality of life of SHG members. But, in the case of vision, Mission & knowledge, p value is >.05, and is not influencing the quality of life of the SHG member. Hypothesis 1 and 2 may be said as accepted by excluding the two factors such as Technical efficiency and vision, mission and knowledge.

10. Conclusion

The self help group is an important instrument to promote entrepreneurial activities among women. All the entrepreneurial efficiency factors except technical efficiency

have the significant relationship with the empowerment factors which indicates that the efficiency factors influence the overall empowerment of women. Similarly, empowerment factors are also showing significant relationship with quality of life, indicating their influence on quality of life of women entrepreneurs. SHG members' Entrepreneurial efficiency does impact the empowerment. It is concluded from this research that SHGs have been successful in empowering women through entrepreneurial efficiency. Consequently empowerment's influence is turning into Quality of life of self help group member in the study area. Thus, women entrepreneurs improved the quality of life and status as members of SHGs.

11. Limitations of the study and Scope for Future Research

As similar to other research studies, this research also has several limitations. This paper investigates only the impact of empowerment and entrepreneurial efficiency on quality of life and further may add life satisfaction. The study limited to Kadapa district only.

References

1. Agrawal, S. 2003. Technology Model for women's empowerment. Kurukshetra. May: 18-28.
2. Chatterjee Shankar (2016), Women Empowerment through Self-help Groups (SHGs): Cases from Telangana State,
3. Endalcachew Bayeh 2016, The role of empowering women and achieving gender equality to the sustainable development of Ethiopia, Pacific Science Review B: Humanities and Social Sciences, 2 (1), 37-42, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psr.2016.09.013>
4. Gopika, Remya John, Elsa M Jose, G. G. (2015). Women Empowerment through Entrepreneurship and Its Glitches: A Theoretical Approach. International Journal of Scientific Research and Management, 3(4). Retrieved from <https://ijsrm.in/index.php/ijsrm/article/view/776>
5. Goswami, Indrajit & Dsilva, Nigel & Chaudhary, Vijeta. (2018). The Role Of Self Help Groups In Women Empowerment In Maharashtra: An Empirical Analysis.
6. Hemavathy Nithyanandhana S & Norma Mansorb (2015), Self Help Groups and Women's Empowerment, Institutions and Economies Vol. 7, No. 2, July 2015, pp. 143-164
7. Jasdeep Maggu (2016), Rural Women Empowerment: Entrepreneurship Development Through SHG, Abhinav International Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Management & Technology, 5(6), 1-8. Retrieved from: http://abhinavjournal.com/journal/index.php/ISSN-2320-0073/article/view/1055/pdf_243
8. Kanakalatha, V (2017), The Socio-Economic Empowerment of Women through Self Help Groups -An Empirical Study.
9. Kimpah, Jeniboy & Raudeliuniene, Jurgita. (2014). Impact of women empowerment on work performance: Malaysian Banks.
10. Kondal Kappa (2014), Women Empowerment through Self Help Groups in Andhra Pradesh, India,
11. Lina George & Kumar Krishna (2014), Micro finance for socio-economic empowerment of women – A study of stree shakti programme in the state of Karnataka, International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering, 4 (2), 263-276
12. Meenakshi pattu, Subrahmanyam V, Ravichandran K (2013), Entrepreneurship as a Tool for the Empowerment of Rural Women in India, IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS) 13 (5), 07-12
13. Mochi Pankaj & Vahoniya, Dilip (2015), Role of self-help group in life of rural women, Advance Research Journal of Social Science, 6(1), 71-76 DOI: 10.15740/HAS/ARJSS/6.1/71-76
14. Murthy, Psr, Economic Empowerment of Rural Women by Self Help Group through Micro Credit (December 22, 2012). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2193045> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2193045>

15. Neha Pandey. (2014). Women Empowerment: Questioning Gender Equality in Cotemporary Society. Online International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. Volume IV, Issue VI Nov-Dec 2014.
16. Rajalingam, Yasothai & Jauhar, Junaimah & Haji Abdul Ghani, Ahmad Bashawir & Professor, Bashawir. (2015). A Study on the Impact of Empowerment on Employee Performance: The Mediating Role of Appraisal. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science. 3. 92.
17. Stanzin Mantok, (2016) " Role of Women Entrepreneurship in Promoting Women Empowerment " , International Journal of Management and Applied Science (IJMAS) , pp. 204-207, Volume-2, Issue-9, Special Issue-1
18. Sharma, Preeti & Kanta Varma, Shashi. (2008). Women Empowerment through Entrepreneurial Activities of Self Help Groups. Indian Research Journal of Extension Education. 8. 46-51.
19. Subramaniam Geetha, Tanb Peck-Leong, Maniam Balasundram, Ershad Ali (2013), Workplace Flexibility, Empowerment and Quality of Life , Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 105 885 – 893
20. Vijayalakshmi, D, Narayana Gowda K, Jamuna K.V., Babu Ray R.M. and Jyoti T. Sajjan(2012), Empowerment of Self Help Group Women through Value Addition of finger millet,
21. WHOQOL: Measuring Quality of Life, World Health Organization (1997), Retrived from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3395923/>